

FAIRSFair
Fostering Fair Data Practices in Europe

Developing sustainable business models

Key issue #2 in Assessing Capability Maturity and Engagement with FAIR-enabling Practices (ACME-FAIR)

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Introduction

Research performing organisations (RPOs) are expected to provide a service offering professional support for researchers to produce and use FAIR outputs. A wide variety of internal and external stakeholders are likely to influence RPO expectations. Prominent among these will be the data policies and contractual requirements of relevant Research Funding Organisations. The strategies and guidance available from the EOSC Association, EOSC projects, national governments, university associations, scientific societies, and professional groups are all likely to shape an individual RPOs own policy and strategy on the scope of its research data management services that will be needed to help implement FAIR principles, and these will need to respond to ‘bottom-up’ demands and challenges identified by researchers themselves.

Taking action in this complex landscape requires collaboration across the organisation, involving core Research Office, Library and IT services, and drawing specialist advice from Human Resources, Legal or Commercialisation units (for example). Establishing and maintaining a service will most probably involve team effort to set measurable objectives over the short, medium, and long terms. Regardless of the maturity of the service, the team will need to consider (or review) how it addresses such questions as ‘who are our customers or beneficiaries? What is the value offered to them? What are the key capabilities, roles and relationships we need to deliver them? How will we resource the costs of providing them?’ This guide aims to offer a basis for productive discussion among the people involved in addressing such questions.

The report ‘Turning FAIR into Reality’ (TFIR) issued by the European Commission in 2018 provides guidance for practitioners and research performing organisations (RPOs) on making choices about implementing FAIR. It says that “for FAIR data practices to be reliably supported, there need to be sustainable business models and investment in all the components to ensure the support ecosystem is robust”. It also acknowledges that “these models need to rely on compatible income streams, since user-based income in the form of access fees will be limited,” and that “while there is no single, optimal business model, it is essential that the value proposition, community support and policy context is carefully aligned”.¹ This will help make the case for resourcing, which is likely to be negotiated through national agreements with relevant Research Funding Organisations. Science Europe offers further high-level guidance on financial aspects in its *Practical Guide to Sustainable Research Data*.²

¹ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, (2018). *Turning FAIR into reality : final report and action plan from the European Commission expert group on FAIR data*, Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/54599> (p.57)

² Tommaso Boccali, Anne Elisabeth Sølvsnes, Mark Thorley, Stefan Winkler-Nees, & Marie Timmermann. (2021). *Practical Guide to Sustainable Research Data*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4769703>

Introducing ACME-FAIR

ACME-FAIR is a set of guides produced in the FAIRsFAIR project, whose main purpose is to help those managing and delivering relevant professional services to self-assess how they are enabling researchers, and colleagues who support them, to put the FAIR principles into practice (for short we refer to this as ‘FAIR-enabling practice’). ACME-FAIR can be used independently, or it can be used to complement Science Europe’s *Practical Guide to Sustainable Research Data*.³ Both guides include ‘capability maturity’ matrices (or ‘rubrics’), for Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) e.g. universities, research institutes. While Science Europe’s guide targets their strategic-level management, **ACME-FAIR aims to support the operational levels of the organisation**. It can optionally be used to follow up an assessment based on the Science Europe maturity matrices. ACME-FAIR is also strongly informed by the recommendations of the European Commission’s Expert Group on FAIR data, *Turning FAIR into Reality*.⁴

Covering key practical issues

ACME-FAIR covers 7 key issues for FAIR-enabling practice themes highlighted by FAIRsFAIR, in response to recommendations from the *Turning FAIR into Reality* report, and issues covered by the Science Europe *Guide to Sustainable Research Data*. The table below shows how the FAIRsFAIR and Science Europe guides complement each other.

1. Defining the policy environment	- Policy environment
2. Developing sustainable business models	- Financial aspects
3. Professionalising roles through training, mentoring, and recognition	- Training
4. Supporting data management planning	} Technical preparedness
5. Defining data interoperability frameworks	
6. Selecting data, services, and repositories for FAIR	
7. Ensuring trusted curation	

Table 1. Mapping key issues addressed in ACME-FAIR (left) to Science Europe’s guidance (right)

The ACM-FAIR guides are a series, with one guide for each of the issues in Table 1. Each includes a brief introduction, together with the explanation above, followed by a checklist describing the scope of the capabilities covered. Each guide then offers a rubric or set of tables describing maturity and community engagement dimensions of these capabilities.

Why use ACME-FAIR?

The ACME-FAIR aims to be useful to services providing researchers with support on FAIR implementation. Its fundamental role is to offer a framework for discussion within and between organisations. It has 3 main use cases:

1. For the service to self-assess its readiness to support FAIR, by establishing current and desired levels of communication and adoption of community practices and the organisational maturity of the support offered for these.

³ Tommaso Boccali, Anne Elisabeth Sølvsnes, Mark Thorley, Stefan Winkler-Nees, & Marie Timmermann. (2021). Practical Guide to Sustainable Research Data. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4769703>

⁴ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, (2018). *Turning FAIR into reality : final report and action plan from the European Commission expert group on FAIR data*, Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/54599> (p.57)

2. Provide a basis for dialogue with colleagues to set out a roadmap for improving on current support, e.g. through training and skills development to improve the communication and adoption of community practices.
3. Support sharing of consistent information between peer organisations about their current levels of maturity and community engagement around FAIR-enabling practices, e.g. with national or international coordination and facilitation.

Organisations that perform research vary a great deal, both in how they are organised internally, and the environments they operate in. No capability model can take all of these factors into account, so anyone involved in planning a roadmap for their organisation's services in this area is likely to want or need more specific guidance on the topics covered. The ACME-FAIR guides will be developed further to reference some of these. FAIRsFAIR also offers a set of examples in the form of 'Implementation Stories' that cover the same themes.⁵

Background

ACME FAIR is partly based on the Digital Curation Centre's *RISE* self-evaluation framework for research data service development⁶, and partly on the guide '*Do I-PASS for FAIR*', which was produced in the context of the Dutch Coordination Point Research Data Management.⁷

ACME FAIR uses a two-dimensional scale, comprising 0-3 maturity levels for each of the 7 issues, and 0-3 levels of communication and adoption of practice. The **maturity levels** are a simplified version of the first 3 levels of the widely adopted *CMMI* (Capability Maturity Model Integration) framework⁸.

The levels of "**community engagement**" are separated out from maturity for the following reasons:

- Community engagement is essential for all of the practice areas covered.
- While the maturity goal of optimising alignment with *organisational* standards and practice is relevant to Research Performing Organisations, for research data support it is equally important to align with *community* standards, as defined by research domains and professional communities of practice.
- Identifying areas where maturity and engagement are at differing levels may be helpful to identify pockets of good practice in one or the other, or areas to target for further action.

Capability dimensions: maturity and community engagement

The maturity and community engagement dimensions both indicate progression from no activity (level 0), through ad-hoc coverage of some practice areas (e.g. varying widely across research projects), through to more standardised approaches across the organisation. The maturity and community engagement dimensions are described in more detail as follows:

Maturity

0. **Not addressed.** The relevant professional services for research support do not coordinate any support capability for researchers in this area of focus. Some staff may help but it is not a formally recognised part of their job.

⁵ <https://fairsfair.eu/implementation-adoption-stories>

⁶ Rans, J and Whyte, A. (2017). 'Using RISE, the Research Infrastructure Self-Evaluation Framework' v.1.1 Edinburgh: Digital Curation Centre: www.dcc.ac.uk/guidance/how-guides

⁷ Taco de Bruin, Sarah Coombs, Jutta de Jong, Irene Haslinger, Henk van den Hoogen, Frans Huigen, Mijke Jetten, Jacko Koster, Margriet Miedema, Sief Öllers, Inge Slouwerhof, Ingeborg Verheul, & Jacqueline Ringersma. (2020). Do I-PASS for FAIR. A self assessment tool to measure the FAIR-ness of an organization (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4080867>

⁸ CCMI. e.g. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Capability_Maturity_Model_Integration

1. **Initial.** May be incomplete and falling short of the intent of the area of focus. Aware of and addressing performance issues.
2. **Managed.** Complete coverage delivering the full intent of the area of focus, minimally in some aspects. Lacking full alignment with overall organisational standards and practice, but identifies and monitors performance objectives. Includes and builds on level 1.
3. **Defined.** Complete coverage that delivers the full intent of the area of focus and aligns with overall organisational standards and practice. Identifies and monitors performance objectives that expand alignment to the whole organisation. Includes and builds on level 2.

Community engagement: practice awareness, adoption, and collaboration

This dimension identifies the level of engagement the organisation (or the relevant services it offers) has with the communities it serves, about maintaining and updating data stewardship practices and identifying new areas for the development of policy and implementation standards. It includes actively communicating and promoting existing and emerging approaches to the immediately impacted communities and the wider data infrastructure landscape.

0. **Not addressed.** The relevant professional services for research support do not coordinate any support capability for researchers in this area of focus. Some staff may help but it is not a formally recognised part of their job.
1. **Awareness:** the service monitors data stewardship practice in the community or communities it serves, and makes local practitioners aware of it.
2. **Adoption:** the service or its host organisation also supports practitioners to embed community practice locally.
3. **Collaboration:** the service also engages with the design, development, and review of community practice. Consults and collaborates widely, potentially also taking a community coordination and leadership role.

Please give us your feedback

The Digital Curation Centre (DCC) maintains ACME-FAIR. Feedback on this guide was gathered in the FAIRsFAIR project, and changes have been made to reflect that. DCC very much welcomes your thoughts on how to improve it further, especially suggestions of guidance to reference on each of its themes. Please give your feedback using this [short questionnaire](#). It asks how far you agree with 4 simple statements, and invites you to add any comments you wish. Please note that it collects no personal information.

ACME Checklist: Developing sustainable business models for FAIR

The ACME-FAIR checklist identifies five main capability areas under this theme. Four capability areas are assessed on the *maturity* scale, measuring integration of the capability with organisation-level standards and practices. One further area is assessed on the *community engagement* scale, measuring adoption of broader community standards and practices.

The Science Europe *Practical Guide to Sustainable Research Data* includes a capability maturity matrix that complements ACME-FAIR at a high level. The relevant capabilities it describes include:

- Financial aspects: access to funding for the RPO and how the funding is used to support data sharing and interoperability.
- Organisational engagement and commitment: acknowledging the need to develop solutions for sustainable research data and being committed to seek alignment of approaches with other research stakeholders (such as other RPOs, funders, infrastructures, research communities).

The scales used in the Science Europe guide are broadly consistent with ACME-FAIR. It may be helpful to use it prior to using ACME-FAIR, but this is not necessary to use ACME-FAIR effectively.

As a first step, consider the capabilities in the checklist below that are relevant to your organisation. This may help you narrow down your goals in using ACME-FAIR, which might include assessing only those capabilities already under development, only those under consideration, or both.

Which capabilities is your organisation developing or considering doing in future?

Maturity	Current	Considering
1) Defining the value of research support capabilities for enabling FAIR?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2) Committing to sustainable resourcing of FAIR infrastructures?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3) Reviewing the roles and responsibilities for enabling FAIR outputs?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4) Service roadmap definition and review?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Engagement		
5) Monitoring researchers' data stewardship competences and capacity for FAIR?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

To identify or review a model for the service it is highly desirable to establish a working group with senior management support. This should involve all relevant areas of the organisation's research support services and governance, e.g. Research Committee, Research Ethics Committee, IT Services, Archive or Research Data Management service.

The next step in using ACME-FAIR is to discuss with the relevant colleagues what can realistically be achieved to meet needs of researchers, other stakeholders such as funders, and the organisation. To inform that, you may find the scope notes below helpful. They describe each capability for this theme covered in the framework.

Scope

Below we define capabilities in this area, and then describe levels of maturity and engagement.

Defining the value of research support capabilities for enabling FAIR

- Identifying the value proposition and beneficiaries/ customers of the support to be offered
- Defining the costs, risks, and challenges that researchers face at key points in the research data lifecycle, how the service addresses them now, and how it will do in the short, medium and long-term
- Identifying measurable benefits and objectives that align with research data management processes

Committing to sustainable resourcing of FAIR infrastructures

- Scoping the business planning for FAIR-enabling infrastructure and services, recognising that Research Funding Organisations consider investment returns to be greater when research outputs are FAIR
- Identifying a cost model for allocating resources to FAIR-enabling services, taking into account relevant internal services, and services available externally e.g. from Research Data Infrastructures
- Monitoring the cost-effectiveness of services, and their fulfilment of objectives e.g. for compliance with requirements for FAIR outputs and research data strategy.

Reviewing the roles and responsibilities for enabling FAIR outputs

- Getting a shared understanding of capabilities the various research support services have to enable FAIR, and reviewing how roles and responsibilities for this will be split between the key actors
- Defining the level of staffing needed for all central service roles to help researchers with FAIR data stewardship, considering the policy, infrastructure and research liaison aspects of these roles
- Allocating roles to cover the whole research data lifecycle, and agreeing the performance requirements of these roles to meet all stakeholder expectations.

Service roadmap definition and review

- Reviewing the capabilities that will need to be developed to deliver FAIR-enabling services, taking account of services available both internally and externally, and identifying priorities
- Aligning plans with organisational objectives, and setting short, medium, and long-term priorities with definition of how success will be measured, and how FAIR criteria will be applied to research outputs
- Reviewing gaps in provision and potential for better service integration to meet new requirements, considering developments in FAIR-enabling services available externally, e.g. through the EOSC.

Monitoring researchers' data stewardship competences and capacity for FAIR

- Engaging with researchers to assess current levels of general competences needed for FAIR, and their capacity to apply these competences, considering the current availability of support with this
- Consulting on opportunities to fill gaps in domain-relevant practices, considering areas of strength and weakness in the wider community and in the adoption of these practices locally
- Enabling research staff to contribute to development of the service model for enabling FAIR implementation, and to domain-relevant approaches to applying FAIR to their outputs.

ACME Rubric: Developing sustainable business models for FAIR

Developing sustainable business models for FAIR	Maturity			Maturity level (0-3)
	1) Initial	2) Managed	3) Defined	
Developing sustainable business models for FAIR	<p>1) Initial May be incomplete and falling short of the intent of the area of focus. Aware of and addressing performance issues</p>	<p>2) Managed Delivering the full intent of the area of focus, though minimally in some aspects. Lacking full alignment with overall organisational standards and practice, but identifies and monitors performance objectives. Includes and builds on level 1.</p>	<p>3) Defined Complete coverage that delivers the full intent of the area of focus and aligns with overall organisational standards and practice. Identifies and monitors performance objectives that expand alignment to the whole organisation. Includes and builds on level 2.</p>	Maturity level (0-3)
Defining the value of research support capabilities for enabling FAIR	<p>Our research support strategy acknowledges the value to our organisation of good research data management. We are learning about the cost factors in making data FAIR (e.g. data complexity), and the costs of our organisation's research data not being FAIR (e.g. storage duplication). We are considering these costs together with risks (e.g. non-compliance with funder expectations), challenges (e.g. culture change) and benefits of FAIR (e.g. analytic opportunities from machine-actionable data).</p>	<p>Our research support strategy sets out the benefits to the organisation of support for FAIR at key points in the research data lifecycle (e.g. data management planning, data archiving). The beneficiaries are identified (e.g. funded research projects, Phd students) alongside how their data management risks or costs are reduced. Our strategy recognises that FAIRness of data can be a criterion for long-term sustainability, and it is neither feasible nor necessary to manage all research data for ever.</p>	<p>The organisation has adopted a strategy to ensure research data of long-term value are 'born' FAIR and remain FAIR in the future. The strategy identifies measurable benefits to the organisation. It links these to processes for managing the risks and costs of making data FAIR, and of sustaining access to reusable data of long-term value.</p>	

Developing sustainable business models for FAIR	<p>1) Initial May be incomplete and falling short of the intent of the area of focus. Aware of and addressing performance issues</p>	<p>2) Managed Delivering the full intent of the area of focus, though minimally in some aspects. Lacking full alignment with overall organisational standards and practice, but identifies and monitors performance objectives. Includes and builds on level 1.</p>	<p>3) Defined Complete coverage that delivers the full intent of the area of focus and aligns with overall organisational standards and practice. Identifies and monitors performance objectives that expand alignment to the whole organisation. Includes and builds on level 2.</p>	<p>Maturity level (0-3)</p>
<p>Committing to sustainable resourcing of FAIR infrastructures</p>	<p>Business planning for our research support services recognises Research Funders consider their investment returns to be greater when the outputs of the research are FAIR. It acknowledges the need for machine-actionability of FAIR outputs to assist in monitoring this investment. Our plans are incomplete, but commit core funding towards developing services that are high priority for making research outputs FAIR.</p>	<p>Our research support model commits to developing FAIR-enabling services, and applies a cost model for allocating resources to these, e.g. based on staff time and service usage. We have sustainable resourcing for services offering researchers the capabilities to take advantage of machine-actionable data management plans.</p> <p>We engage with Research Funding Organisations, Research Data Infrastructures, publishers and other key partners to identify opportunities for shared resourcing of open infrastructure for FAIR research outputs.</p>	<p>Our organisation invests in services that make our researchers' outputs FAIR, and help them to use FAIR outputs. We monitor cost-effectiveness of these services and our capabilities to provide these in-house, or from external providers where relevant. Our services also monitor to what extent research outputs match those stated in data management plans, and are FAIR, considering explained deviations from plans and agreed exceptions to the applicability of FAIR criteria.</p>	
<p>Reviewing the roles and responsibilities for enabling FAIR outputs</p>	<p>Our research support services have a shared understanding of their respective capabilities for enabling FAIR data production. To inform a business model of how our support service will operate, we are reviewing the roles needed, and how the responsibilities for them are split between key actors, e.g. research office, library, IT services, legal, and commercialisation units.</p>	<p>We have a support service model defining the level of staffing needed for all central service roles to help researchers with FAIR data stewardship. These roles cover most of the research data lifecycle and are defined by referring to available competence frameworks for FAIR data stewardship. There is regular review to ensure a balance between roles relating to policy, infrastructure, and researcher liaison, reflecting the needs of the organisation.</p>	<p>Our organisation's service model defines and allocates the responsibilities for providing services, to cover the whole research data lifecycle. The performance requirements of these are defined and monitored to ensure the research environment is enabling FAIR outputs to meet expectations of the organisation, its research funders, data users, and stakeholder groups. The model includes restricted data access, where there are privacy and confidentiality requirements</p>	

Developing sustainable business models for FAIR	1) Initial May be incomplete and falling short of the intent of the area of focus. Aware of and addressing performance issues	2) Managed Delivering the full intent of the area of focus, though minimally in some aspects. Lacking full alignment with overall organisational standards and practice, but identifies and monitors performance objectives. Includes and builds on level 1.	3) Defined Complete coverage that delivers the full intent of the area of focus and aligns with overall organisational standards and practice. Identifies and monitors performance objectives that expand alignment to the whole organisation. Includes and builds on level 2.	Maturity level (0-3)
Service roadmap definition and review	We have a basic plan to deliver some of the capabilities needed for FAIR-enabling services. This takes into consideration the scope of services available to our organisation, e.g. from Research Data Infrastructures. We have defined priorities for establishing support capabilities to meet FAIR data policy expectations of our organisation, relevant Research Funding Organisations, and other key stakeholders.	We have reviewed all the capabilities needed to provide FAIR-enabling services, and how the development of these aligns with broader organisational services for research support. Our roadmap sets out short, medium and long-term priorities to fill gaps. We have defined how success will be measured, using FAIR criteria for evaluating research outputs, and considering stakeholders' recommendations for FAIR services.	Our organisation periodically reviews its service development roadmap to ensure we respond to new developments in FAIR-enabling services in EOSC, and the broader community. These plans identify gaps in our current provision and identifies potential for improved integration of services and infrastructure. The roadmap addresses opportunities for better integration of services to deal with all FAIR outputs across the research lifecycle, and to ensure these outputs are reusable for social and economic benefit.	

	Community engagement: Practice awareness, adoption and collaboration			
Developing sustainable business models for FAIR	1) Awareness: the organisation monitors community practice and makes local practitioners aware of it.	2) Adoption: the organisation also supports practitioners to embed community practice locally. Includes and builds on level 1.	3) Collaboration: the organisation also engages with the design, development, and review of community practice. Consults and collaborates widely, potentially also taking a community coordination and leadership role. Includes and builds on level 2.	Engagement level (0-3)
Monitoring researchers' data stewardship competences and capacity for FAIR	We engage with researchers through faculty structures to raise awareness of general cross-domain competences involved in making research outputs FAIR, e.g. to consider FAIR in their data management planning, use domain-relevant metadata, resources and repositories. Business planning reflects our knowledge of researchers' capacity to apply these competences, considering the availability of research support services to assist in this at faculty and central levels.	We gather information on the current levels of adoption of domain-based practices to enable FAIR, and reflect this in our service model. Our model addresses the relative strengths and weaknesses of the domain-relevant standards, services, and resources available from research communities, both locally and globally. We consult research faculty on our model and development roadmap, to consider opportunities for the service to fill domain-relevant gaps more effectively.	Our organisation enables research staff to contribute to development of our service model for enabling FAIR implementation. Research staff are incentivised to contribute their domain expertise towards development of FAIR implementation approaches. These meet needs of domain-specific communities of practice, e.g., in identifying which research data should be managed and made FAIR, for how long it should be preserved, and which categories should be made openly accessible.	